

Solid oxide fuel cell combined heat and power: Future-ready Energy

DELIVERABLE D3.6

System architecture freeze to proceed with build-up

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In accordance with preliminary performance maps (D2.1) and short stack characterization tests (D2.2), as well as the PFD of the SO-FREE system developed by ICI, reported in D3.3, and the data provided by IEN in D3.4, USGM has developed the simulation of SO-FREE system in Aspen Plus®. The simulation phase, provided information on temperature, composition, and flow rates at the inlet and outlet of each reactor/combustor which were used by ICI for the development of the real system's P&ID and the subsequent selection of components for the build-up of the SO-FREE pilot plant.

Due to budget constraints within the SO-FREE project, ICI and USGM undertook significant additional efforts in simulation, industrial design, and supplier interfacing to develop a system that could meet project requirements while remaining within financial limitations. Extensive work was required both in simulation and industrial design to develop a functional configuration integrating multiple technologies into a single setup while maintaining cost efficiency. The main challenge was not only to find suppliers and solutions capable of meeting budget constraints but also to ensure that the selected components were available on the market and backed by reliable industrial suppliers. Indeed in addition to budget limitations, the project faced significant challenges in sourcing critical high-temperature components, such as blowers and valves. These components are produced by only a handful of suppliers, making it risky to rely on a single provider. This dependency not only increases costs and extends delivery times but also poses a serious risk for future industrialization, where supply chain flexibility is crucial. Moreover, since these components are not yet widely industrialized due to the lack of a consolidated market, they have undergone limited development and testing, increasing the likelihood of malfunctions or performance issues. To mitigate these risks, the selection process had to prioritize not only cost but also the reliability of the suppliers and the maturity of the components. The aim was to avoid integrating elements that were still at a prototypical stage, as this would have introduced additional technical uncertainties into the system. As a result, the workflow followed a cyclical process, where system simulations were first conducted to identify an efficient and cost-effective configuration, followed by the development of a P&ID based on the simulations. Subsequently, suppliers were consulted to obtain cost estimates and assess component availability and reliability. If supplier costs exceeded the budget, or the proposed components lacked sufficient industrial validation, the entire process had to be restarted from the simulation phase to refine a new viable configuration.

The extensive effort invested in cost optimization while ensuring the technical feasibility of the system underscores the strategic role of simulation and industrial design in successfully delivering the SO-FREE project within budget. Given the significant additional work required to refine the system configuration, iteratively adapt the design to both budget and market constraints, and engage with suppliers to ensure feasibility, the delivery of this Report was delayed, causing also a knock-on effect on subsequent tasks related to component sourcing, design review, system assembly, delivery to testing sites, demo testing and corollary reporting.

2 FIRST DESIGN CYCLE

In accordance with preliminary performance maps (D2.1) and short stack characterization tests (D2.2), as well as the process flow diagram (PFD) of the SO-FREE system developed by ICI, reported in D3.3, and the data provided by IEN in D3.4, USGM developed the first draft of the system simulation in Aspen Plus®, which was preparatory to the development of the real system's P&ID and the selection of components. It provides information on temperature, composition, and flow rates at the inlet and outlet of each reactor/combustor. This allows for an informed approach to catalyst selection and the proper sizing of both the reactors and other components (e.g. piping, valves) for the SO-FREE system.

From the first Aspen simulation and based on cost reduction and design improvements considerations for the system, ICI developed an initial Piping and Instrumentation Diagram (P&ID) for the SO-FREE system, which was also reviewed for conformity to applicable standards (D4.1).

Compared to the simulation carried out by USGM a blower was introduced for anode recirculation. This component would have had a maximum operating temperature of approximately 850°C. To ensure its durability, a heat exchanger was added to the recirculation line with the double purpose of lowering the recirculation temperature below 700°C and rising up the temperature of the input fuel. Also the modulating valve for fuel bypass and air recirculation are critical components, as they should not operate at high temperatures to avoid excessive costs.

3 SECOND DESIGN CYCLE

Following the modifications made to the first P&ID and the guidelines provided by the project partners ICI, IEN and AVL, USGM developed a second version of the Aspen simulation. The simulated SOFC system is truly flexible, and allows the operation of two different SOFC stack technologies fed with three different fuels: 100% H₂, 100%CH₄ and 50%H₂-50% CH₄, but also for varying percentages of H₂ and CH₄. The architecture system is composed of an autothermal reformer connected to an SOFC stack, a burner, a heat recovery system incorporating four heat exchangers and different splitters /mixers.

Compared to the previous design cycle, in this case, a single fuel inlet stream has been set up, with its composition varying depending on the specific case under analysis. Additionally, unlike the initial design, after being compressed the fuel is preheated using exhaust gases from the burner.

The described SOFC system was validated with the experimental data from short stack characterization tests reported in D2.2 and results show good agreement, with anodic output compositions differences below 2.5% between experimental and simulated results for the same anodic input.

Implementing the P&ID showed that the cost of operating a high-temperature valve is lower than the cost of integrating two heat exchangers. Additionally, system performance is improved, as the recirculation can be cooled more effectively than in the previous case, allowing the blower to operate under better conditions while optimizing equipment and space utilization.

For security reasons, especially during start up and shut down phases, the capability to discharge part of the fuel entering the anode or a portion of the recirculation stream, venting it outside the system, was

considered. This control mechanism is not intended for regular operation but should be used only in case of anomalies to avoid operation outside the ranges especially at the anode compartment of the stack and at the blower. In order to avoid the need of high temperature valves to vent out the fuel or the recirculation, an upstream water/gas heat exchange was implemented, which can also be used to collect gas samples for analyzing the inlet and outlet compositions of the stack module.

4 FINAL DESIGN CYCLE AND COMPONENTS SELECTION

Once the final simulation and P&ID were validated, it was possible to proceed with the selection of the components. At this stage, in order to keep system costs under control, it was necessary to further and substantially modify the P&ID of the real plant to address various operational requirements.

The main modification concerns the operating range of the blower. To significantly reduce costs (from €50k to €2-3k) and delivery times (from approximately six months to few weeks), it was necessary to rethink the blower's operation to enable it to function at lower temperatures (around 150°C). To implement this change, the recirculated flow exiting the stack exchanges heat with upstream flows and an ambient-temperature air stream to better control outlet temperatures. The further modifications have eliminated the need for a high-temperature three-way valve, thereby reducing both costs and operational risks for the plant.

Following the definition of the final plant layout, it was possible to select the BoP components that will be used for the build-up of the prototype plant. The quoted prices for purchasing one prototype plant amount to € 200,886.35 , showing the actual cost of manufacture of each system – and the tightness of the constraint on the system integrator's budget.

5 NEXT STEPS

The next step will be functional testing at ICI. Once the system has been fully integrated, tested, and its control logic optimized, it will be transported to KIWA (or IEN) for comprehensive validation of all functions and control procedures.